

Does Regularity Captured in an LMS Relate to Students' Performance in Courses of an Online Degree Program? A Case Study

Teodora Dogaru, Agathe Merceron^[0000-0003-1015-5359], Julian Fröhlich, and
Petra Sauer

Berliner Hochschule für Technik, Luxemburgerstrasse 10, 13353 Berlin, Germany
{merceron, sauer}@bht-berlin.de

Abstract. In this paper, we consider an online study program that is attended by students who mostly work full-time and therefore study part-time. We investigate whether relationships can be found between students' interactions in online courses of this program and their performance in courses. Though the study program and the courses are both online, their delivery through the learning management system (LMS) Moodle has not been designed to store comprehensive student interactions automatically. Therefore, we investigated whether the weekly regularity of students in the LMS is correlated to their performance in the course. Weekly regularity has been introduced in the context of MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) in [5]. We obtained inconclusive results. In only a few courses we could find a strong or moderate correlation. We conjecture that this might be due to two factors: the limitation of our dataset and the fact that, in the context of an online degree program, successful students do not necessarily access the learning material on a regular weekly basis.

Keywords: Learning Management Systems · Analysis of Moodle Log Data · Regularity · Student Performance · Online Degree Program · Online Course.

1 Introduction

The study presented in this paper has taken place within the DiSEA project¹ which is concerned with investigating factors leading to students' success or dropout in online degree programs. Online degree programs are less common than classical so-called face-to-face study programs. In Germany, for example, only 4.9% of the degree programs in higher education in 2024 are distance learning programs, including the online degree program considered in this work [9].

The present study considers the online undergraduate program "Computer Science and Media" started in 2001. It is offered in the framework of a network of German public universities of applied sciences called VFH². Casual surveys

¹ <https://disea-projekt.de/>

² <https://www.vfh.de/>

show that many of the students enrolled in this online degree work full-time or have small children or relatives they take care of (note that universities do not store data on this aspect) and, therefore, study part-time. Most students enrolled in this degree would not be able to attend a classical degree program with face-to-face teaching and a fixed schedule. Compared to classical face-to-face programs offered in the same universities, the dropout rate is higher as investigated by [11]; this has also been observed by others, for example, [3]. In our context, dropping out does not necessarily mean failure, see [16]. For example, some students can get a better job thanks to the skills and knowledge they have acquired after studying a few courses and, thus, quit the program before obtaining the degree.

When enrolling in the program, students choose one university of the network. The syllabus, the credits, and the standard multi-media course material that is available in the learning management system (LMS) are the same for all universities offering this online degree. The standard course material contains reading material, videos, animations, quizzes, worked-out exercises as well as tests and assignments; the number of these elements may vary, depending on the courses. It is worth noting that this material in most courses is developed with authoring tools independent of the LMS. From the beginning, this design decision has been taken to decouple the multimedia course material developed for the network from any specific learning platform. Thus, students' interactions with the material such as watching a video or answering a quiz are not captured by the LMS, only clicking on the link leading to the material is recorded in the log files of the LMS, in our case Moodle.

Each university appoints its teaching staff; except for a few optional courses, the teaching staff is not shared among the universities. Like in face-to-face teaching, teachers can conduct their online courses in their own way. For example, they can encourage the usage of the forum, or not, or, in addition to - or even instead of - the standard material of the course provided by the network, they are free to use any teaching material they like as long as they follow the syllabus. They can give feedback on assignments via the LMS, emails, or synchronous meetings. Teachers offer weekly or bi-monthly synchronous online meetings, as well as two to four in-class meetings in a semester. Depending on the courses, these meetings can be mandatory or optional.

To investigate graduation and dropout in the above-mentioned online programs, we take a data-centric approach. We have obtained two datasets from two universities. One set, the academic dataset, contains the courses students enrolled in and the marks they obtained. The second set is the interaction data of the students with the LMS from the summer semester 2022 till the summer semester 2023. As the log files, which contain the interaction data, are deleted after 30 days, we used only the interaction data of students who have opted in and thus agreed to longer storage and use. We merged the two datasets so that we could associate the students' interaction data in a course with their performance, which means the mark students got in this course. In the present case study, we analyse students' interactions in the LMS and investigate whether a relation between regularity as defined in [5] and course performance can be found.

The final aim is to provide students with feedback on their learning behaviours that could support them in doing well in the course. This research complies with the data protection and security regulations of our university and with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union).

Our research question is: Is there any relationship between weekly regular activity in the LMS and performance in courses of the online undergraduate study program Computer Science and Media?

The paper is organized as follows. The following section describes related works that investigate relationships between students' interactions in online courses delivered with a learning management system and students' performance in courses. Section 3 introduces the collected data, its preprocessing, transformation, and some of its limitations, and explains the calculation of the weekly regularity. Section 4 shows and discusses the results that we have obtained. Finally, the last section summarizes our findings, discusses the limitations of this study, and presents future work.

2 Related Works

Looking for relations between students' interactions in a learning system and their performance in a course has already been investigated in many works. It has been particularly extensively studied in the context of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), see [12] for an overview. However, the online courses studied in the present work are no MOOCs.

A work similar to our endeavour is Course Signals developed and used at Purdue University in classical face-to-face courses [2]; Course Signals uses several components to predict students' performance or risk status, one being the amount of points the students have earned in the course so far as recorded in the LMS. Templehaar et al. have used interaction data in an LMS, results of quizzes and assignments in online labs, and students' answers to their learning dispositions to predict performance in a large face-to-face course [15]. From all the data used, the results of quizzes had the most impact on predicting students' performance. Baker et al. were able to show for an online course offered by a private university that students who engage with the online materials early and regularly in the course and complete corresponding course assignments are more likely to pass the course successfully [3]. Švábenský et al. [17] use students' interactions in the Canvas LMS during the three semesters of the Covid pandemic to predict whether students will have a grade smaller than average in a course, which is different from pass and fail. Though all courses are regular courses of face-to-face study programs, during the pandemic they were taught online. The authors calculated a rich set of 27 features including the number of resources accessed, the number of uploaded homework files, the number of submissions that were not passed the deadline, and so on. Another example is the work of Hoq et al., [10], which predicts students' performance in a programming course delivered in a classical face-to-face program. The authors use the programming assignment submission of the students to build their prediction models and have obtained

encouraging results. All these works suggest that it is important for courses in LMS to contain regular assignments or tests and their results to predict students' performance. In contrast, Andergassen et al. investigated the relationship between students' behaviours in three online courses to practice for the exam and the exam results [1]. These courses last for two weeks and are open shortly before the exam after a face-to-face course is finished. The authors used features such as the number of different days students visited the course, the number of exercises solved, or the time spent. Results of exercises or assignments were not available. None of the features used had a strong correlation with students' performance. This result suggests that the context of an online course, here a practice course, matters. Our context differs from these related works in two aspects. First, we consider online courses from an online study program, not face-to-face courses. Second, we do not aim to focus on a particular online course like done in [3], but want to investigate courses of the online undergraduate program "Computer Science and Media" offered by a network of public universities.

A work that is near to our context is the one of Bañeres et al. at the Open University of Catalogna [4]. Any online course has a minimum number of three assignments whose results are stored in a central data mart. Bañeres et al. used these assignments' results to predict at different time intervals the performance of students in the course. While the standard course material of the courses of the online degree programs considered in our project does have regular assignments, varying from two to 12, there is no systematic access to the results of the assignments in the LMS or any data mart as teachers are free on how they communicate the results to students, a contrast to the work presented in [4]. The approach of [4] could be adopted in some courses but not in all courses in our context.

Bourajani et al. [5] take a different approach and investigate students' regularity in a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). They propose several formulas to define students' regularity, in particular three formulas that quantify the weekly regularity of students. In their case study, these three measures are strongly correlated (value above 0.9) and, from all regularity measures they have defined, correlate the most with the final grade in the course (correlation value of 0.70). We interpret the results of [5] as follows. Students in a MOOC usually work or study somewhere else. The MOOC is an extra activity and they have to find time for it. Students who do well plan regular time slots in their weekly schedule to study the material delivered each week in the LMS and, in the end, earn a good grade in the final exam. Thus, weekly regularity is a proxy for good time management and motivation which leads to good results in the final exam of the MOOC. We see similarities with the students enrolled in the online degrees considered in our project. Most of these students work full-time or have small children or relatives they take care of. They have to be organised and find time in their schedule to study the online material of the courses. Thus, we conjectured that weekly regularity could also correlate with good grades in courses of the online study programs of the VFH. The contribution of this work is to investigate whether this conjecture holds. If yes, services to support students

in their learning such as notifications about regular work in the LMS could be developed.

However, there is an important difference between our context and the context of [5]. We do not consider a MOOC but regular courses of an online study program. Brun et al. have investigated regularity in courses of a face-to-face study program and found a rather weak correlation, 0.27, between regularity in the LMS and marks [6]. This result suggests that the result described in [5] might not generalize to other online courses offered in other contexts, like our context of online courses of an online study program instead of MOOCs.

3 Data and Methodology

In this section, we explain the data collection, the necessary preprocessing and transformations that were performed, and how we calculated regularity.

3.1 Data

We collect our data via the Moodle platform used to deliver the courses of the VFH online degree programs. The policy of the VFH network is that students should be able to access any course that they have ever taken in their studies. Therefore, for each course of a degree, a new Moodle course is created each semester for the students who enroll in that course in that semester. For example, there are multiple Moodle courses "Medien Design 1" all containing the same standard learning material; they differ in the university and in the semester they were offered and, consequently, in the students enrolled and in the teacher who taught the course.

Only the Moodle logs of users who consented to the use of their data via a consent plug-in built specifically for the DiSEA project were used. The first time users accessed a course, they were required to decide whether or not to share their data with our project. Each week, either new users consented to the use of their log data or existing users withdrew their consent, resulting in a constantly changing data set.

We collected the logs every 7 days using a specific SQL query that was developed at the beginning of the project. This SQL query directly accesses the VFH's Moodle database and only collects log data from users who have given their consent to the use of their data. The collected logs are then encrypted and stored in a CSV file, which is available for download. Originally, the Moodle logs were not designed for data mining analysis, but were mainly used to maintain the learning management system. As a result, many of the fields stored in the logs are not relevant to the purposes of our project. Therefore, we designed the above SQL query to select only those columns that are relevant to the definition of tasks (see below), while discarding all others.

After decrypting the downloaded data, the fields `userid` and `relateduserid`, which contain the identifications (IDs) of the users, were pseudonymized. For log

Table 1. Example of a log entry. Here, user 1361 has sent a message via the Moodle messaging system to another user (=relateduserid) who has not consented to the use of his data. The event for this case would be (core, message, sent).

id	timecreated	userid	relateduserid	courseid	component	action	target
110051230	1642761738	1361	-2	0	core	sent	message

entries where only one user between `userid` and `relateduserid` consented to the use of their data, the other user was set to -2 (see Table 1).

To cope with the ever-growing amount of log data and to keep only the data relevant to our purpose, we needed to reduce the amount of data. To this end, we have developed three strategies: a) We focused exclusively on logs documenting student activity and deleted log data from other Moodle users such as system administrators, guests, lecturers, etc. b) We have focused on components that occur frequently enough (at least 600 log entries) to be relevant for analysis. c) We focused on Moodle courses with at least 75 entries to be able to analyze student behavior. These numbers, 600 and 75, have been decided after data exploration.

After selecting relevant log entries, the data must first be processed before an analysis of student behavior can be performed. To process our data, we applied the methodology presented by Rotelli and Monreale, [13,14], to define a learning activity as a task and calculate its duration. A task is defined as a sequence of interactions of a user within a Moodle learning module, where each interaction is represented by a single log entry. This process comprises three steps: the redefinition and adaptation of the components, the calculation of the duration, and the creation of the task.

In Moodle, each interaction or event is described by an action that is performed on a component, at a specific time, in a specific Moodle course or area of the platform. The components correspond to the modules of the platform, such as dashboard, quiz, assignment, core, etc. The core events are logged at the system level of Moodle, although they might represent actions performed by the user in specific modules, like a user sending a message to another user, see Table 1.

In order to avoid loss of information and a possible misunderstanding of user behavior, the events with the core component must be redefined. Such events are assigned to a component with related content. For example, the event of Table 1 is reassigned to the component Chat. We have defined a total of 29 components, see [7] for the complete list.

After transforming the dataset by redefining and customizing the components, we added a “Duration” column to each row. The goal is to derive from the events how much time a user has spent learning with a specific component and, in the end, with the Moodle platform. To determine the duration of events, we first created a chronologically ordered time series of all events of each user.

Based on this time series and taking into account the respective event type ³, we then calculated the duration of an event.

After the components have been redefined and the events enriched with the duration, the individual data records have been grouped into so-called tasks. A task can be defined as a consecutive sequence of log entries with the same component for a user, which together can be interpreted as a single, targeted activity with a specific component (e.g. forum, quiz, submission task) in a course or a specific area of the platform. A task typically consists of a user ID, component, course ID, number of events, start time and duration. We have obtained 616 347 task records from 549 different user IDs in 1243 courses over the period 2021 December 1st to 2023 September 24th. Students' tasks in Moodle were linked to their performance (grades), if available. The grades of students were obtained from the administration of the university. On this basis, a new data set was created, which was used to analyze the relationships between Moodle activities or tasks and students' course success.

It is important to notice that our dataset is subject to the following limitations:

- We only use Moodle data from students who have explicitly consented to their data being analyzed.
- We only have access to the activities registered by Moodle, without interaction data with the interactive learning material created with specific authoring tools; only the click on the link to this material is registered in the Moodle logs.
- We were only able to link Moodle data with academic data from three university semesters between the summer semesters of 2022 and 2023 when exceptions were in place at the universities in the network due to the coronavirus pandemic. In the meantime, the grade 5 (fail) was only entered in the academic data if there was an attempt to cheat. Otherwise, no grade was recorded in the data if an examination was failed.
- Students can take a module without taking the exam. In this case, the activity is monitored in Moodle, but no grade is recorded in the administrative data. These cases cannot be distinguished in the data from the cases with failed exams without a grade, although they are clearly different in terms of content.

3.2 Methodology

The use of the courses in Moodle is very heterogeneous, which can be explained by the fact that the courses vary greatly in their structure (e.g. number of online meetings, number of assignments) and in the number of students involved. In addition, it should be noted that many activities that are relevant for assessing course success are not recorded in Moodle, as in the majority of the courses the

³ According to the system of [14], there are 5 types of events in Moodle. Depending on the type of event, a specific formula is used to calculate the duration.

multimedia learning material is created with authoring tools that are independent of a learning platform; interactions with e.g. quizzes or exercises from this learning material are not recorded as Moodle log data. In addition, activities that are offered via Moodle plugins and are normally tracked by Moodle can also be used without the Moodle platform. An example of this is participation in a BigBlueButton web conference: students do not necessarily access it via the corresponding course in Moodle, but can also access it via the link they have saved. This makes it more difficult to select relevant activities related to student success.

Data exploration did not show any direct link between tasks and course success. Calculated over all courses, the correlation between the number of tasks and the grade is 0.074, and the correlation between the total duration of tasks and the grade is 0.117. Therefore, we decided to analyze student behavior in Moodle independently of the tasks. We investigated whether students with regular activity in Moodle achieved better results in the courses, as proposed and investigated in [5].

Shirvani Boroujeni et al. in [5] propose several definitions for regularity. One of them, the weekly regularity, measures whether students work on similar days of the week throughout the weeks of the course. It can be expressed by a number between 0 and 1. The maximum value of 1 is reached when students are active on exactly the same days every week. Shirvani Boroujeni et al. found in [5] a correlation of 0.7 between weekly regularity and grade in a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course). The weekly regularity can be seen as a proxy for time management, motivation, and regular learning; students who engage regularly with the course achieve better grades in the exam.

From the 616 347 task records mentioned above, we have compiled a dataset that, for each student and each course of the degree program "Computer Science and Media", contains the total number of events of all tasks per day during the semester. Thus a student is represented by as many days as there are in a semester. We have linked this dataset with the grade in the course when this grade was available. This resulted in a dataset containing aggregated information on the Moodle behavior of 382 different students in a total of 133 courses, see the file `connected_course_vector.csv` in [7].

Since courses are very different due to their different structures and number of participants, we, therefore, decided to calculate the correlation between regularity and grade in the course on a course-by-course basis. A disadvantage of the course-by-course correlation analysis is the small number of participants in the courses, which makes the calculation less meaningful, even though for each course we aggregated the Moodle data from two universities and three semesters.

To examine the linear relationship between regularity and grade, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r-value) was calculated as in [5]. The coefficient is easy to interpret as it lies between -1 and 1. Usually, a correlation between -0.3 and 0.3 is considered weak, a correlation between -0.5 and -0.3 or 0.3 and 0.5 is moderate, and a correlation smaller than -0.5 or bigger than 0.5 is strong. A value of 1 means a perfect positive correlation, while a value of -1 means a

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficient, p-value, and number of participants for the courses with the greatest influence on predicting whether students will drop out of the "Computer Science and Media" degree program (Part 1). A moderate and significant value is bold.

	Principles of Programming 1	Human-Computer Communication	Medien Design 1	Medien Design 2	Introduction to Computer Science
coef.	0.10	-0.23	-0.43	0.08	-0.47
p	0.73	0.23	0.12	0.68	0.04
users	54	65	44	53	47

perfect negative correlation. In our case, it is the other way around: a high negative value means that students who were regularly active in Moodle tended to achieve better grades than less regular active students. This is because in the German education system, the best grades (1) are the lowest numbers and the worst grades (4 for pass and 5 for fail) are the highest numbers on the scale.

In order to correctly interpret the significance of the correlation, we calculated the p-value in addition to the Pearson correlation coefficient. The following applies: if the p-value is less than 0.05, the correlation is statistically significant, i.e. the probability that the correlation is due to chance is less than 5%. If, on the other hand, the p-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, the correlation cannot be considered statistically significant, which indicates that the correlation may have arisen by chance.

4 Results and Discussion

In the following, we present the correlation results between regularity and grade in eight courses from the Bachelor of "Computer Science and Media" program; these eight courses have been found to have the greatest influence on predicting whether students will drop out of the degree, see [11].

Our analysis shows that in only three courses: "Introduction to Computer Science", "Principles of Mathematics", and "Communication, Leadership, and Self-Management", there is a moderate /strong and significant correlation between the regularity of activity in Moodle and the grade, see Tables 2 and 3. The moderate correlation obtained for the course "Medien Design 1" is not significant. The result of this analysis does not systematically confirm the results of [5]. It shows that the relationship between activity regularity and grade is different in different courses; it is difficult to make a general statement about the correlation between these two variables.

To obtain robust results and better understand the correlation between activity regularity and grades in different courses, it would be important to have a larger and more representative sample of data collected over a longer period

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficient, p-value, and number of participants for the courses with the greatest influence on predicting whether students will drop out of the "Computer Science and Media" degree program (Part 2). Strong and significant values are bold.

	Principles of Mathematics	Communication, Leadership and Self-Management	Computer Architecture and Operating Systems
coef.	-0.55	-0.71	-0.23
p	0.04	0.01	0.39
users	41	29	38

of time and from a larger number of participants. In addition, the Moodle log data considered in this study is most probably too limited. If students enrolled in the same course in several semesters, and have been active in the online Moodle courses, interaction data that occurred before semester 2022 is missing. If teachers give feedback on assessments via emails to students, the Moodle log data does not contain students' interactions with assessment feedback, and no task with this component is defined. If students store the link to online meetings on their computer, the Moodle log data does not contain the interaction when students click the link to attend an online meeting; such a task is then missing. If students communicate between themselves using another media like WhatsApp and not Moodle Chat, again these interactions are not stored in the Moodle log data and these tasks are missing. By contrast, the MOOC analyzed by Shirvani Boroujeni et al. [5] occurred only once and was delivered on Coursera where more comprehensive student interactions from all students are stored.

Furthermore, the learning material is not delivered weekly like in MOOCs but is available from the beginning of the course. Some students may plan their learning at the beginning of the semester according to their personal schedule (work, travel, and so on) and block some weeks where they learn more and other weeks where they learn less or not at all. These students are well organized, and motivated but this does not translate into a weekly regularity. Thus, weekly regularity might not be the metric that generally correlates well with performance in our context.

5 Conclusion, Limitations, and Future Work

In this work, we have investigated whether we can find a correlation between the weekly regularity of students in the learning platform in online courses and their marks in those courses. The online courses considered here are no MOOCs but the courses of an undergraduate online study program offered by a German network of universities called VFH. We have investigated eight courses that were found to have the most impact on predicting whether students will drop out of

this degree in [11] and used the weekly regularity as defined in [5]. Our results do not confirm the strong correlation found in [5] in the context of one MOOC as we have found a strong correlation in one course only, a moderate correlation in two courses, and a weak or no correlation in five courses. Our results do not align with the work presented in [6] either as we have found a significant strong or moderate correlation in three courses. In [6], the authors have found a weak correlation of 0.27 between regularity and performance in courses of a classical face-to-face undergraduate program. However, the authors of [6] do not give details on whether the correlation could be higher in some courses and weaker in others.

Our work has several limitations. One limitation already mentioned is our dataset. It is limited in several respects. One limitation is the number of students for whom we could link the tasks in Moodle courses and the grades in the course. Four factors influence these numbers: (1) we have used the Moodle interactions from students who consented to the use of their data; (2) we could link the Moodle tasks with a grade in the course only if a grade was present in the administration data of the university; (3) because of the coronavirus pandemic, grades when students failed the exam were not reported; (4) we could use Moodle data from three semesters only.

A second limitation of our dataset is that it does not contain comprehensive Moodle log data of students. None of the online courses considered in our work has been designed to log comprehensive interactions of students in the course, an essential difference with MOOCs and with other works like [2] or [17]. As already written, teachers are free to give feedback to students on their assignments the way they want: via the Moodle course, via emails outside the Moodle course, or via (online) meetings. As another example, students have found an easy way for them to attend online meetings without accessing the corresponding online course. We might not have enough interaction data to calculate reliably the weekly regularity of students.

Another limitation of our dataset is that we do not have interaction data with the rich multi-media learning material. This prevents us from finding components like quizzes that might be good indicators of performance in courses as put in evidence in [15], [3], or [13]. Looking at the activity of students on specific components and investigating the relationship with performance in the course might be a more promising way than calculating regularity; as argued at the end of section 4, weekly regularity in a course might not correlate with a good performance in this course for all students.

In our project, students from our online study program have been included in the loop, see [8]. Future work is to include teachers of the online study program in the design of online courses so that meaningful interactions are logged. The logs of these meaningful interactions would serve to calculate helpful feedback for students, perhaps also for teachers.

Acknowledgments. This study was funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research under the grant number 01PX21001A.

References

1. Andergassen, M., Mödritscher, F., Neumann, G.: Practice and repetition during exam preparation in blended learning courses: Correlations with learning results. *Journal of Learning Analytics* **1**(1), 48–74 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.18608/jla.2014.11.4>
2. Arnold, K., Pistilli, M.: Course signals at purdue: using learning analytics to increase student success. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Learning Analytics & Knowledge (LAK)*. pp. 267–270. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2330601.2330666>
3. Baker, R., Lindrum, D., Lindrum, M.J., Perkowski, D.: Analyzing early at-risk factors in higher education e-learning courses. In: Santos, O., Romero, C., Pechenizkiy, M., Merceron, A., Mitros, P., Luna, J., Mihaescu, C., Moreno, P., Hershkovitz, A., Ventura, S., Desmarais, M. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Educational Data Mining*. pp. 150–155. International Educational Data Mining Society, Madrid, Spain (July 2015)
4. Bañeres, D., Rodriguez, M.E., Guerrero-Roldán, A., Karadeniz, A.: An early warning system to detect at-risk students in online higher education. *Applied Sciences* **2020** **10**(13), 4427 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10134427>
5. Boroujeni, M.S., Sharma, K., Kidziński, Ł., Lucignano, L., Dillenbourg, P.: How to quantify student’s regularity? In: Verbert, K., Sharples, M., Klobučar, T. (eds.) *Adaptive and Adaptable Learning*. pp. 277–291. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2016)
6. Brun, A., Gras, B., Merceron, A.: Building Confidence in Learning Analytics Solutions: Two Complementary Pilot Studies. In: Ifenthaler, D., Gibson, D. (eds.) *Adoption of Data Analytics in Higher Education Learning and Teaching*, pp. 285–303. *Advances in Analytics for Learning and Teaching*, Springer International Publishing, Cham (2020), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-47392-1_15
7. Dogaru, T., Fröhlich, J., Waghela, R., Merceron, A., Sauer, P.: Open educational datasets from the disea project. Tech. rep., Berlin University of Applied Sciences (2024), <https://zenodo.org/records/14025857>
8. Drzyzga, G., Harder, T., Janneck, M.: Participative development of a learning dashboard for online students using traditional design concepts. In: da Silva, H.P., Ciproso, P. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Computer-Human Interaction Research and Applications (CHIRA)*. pp. 176–191. Springer Nature Switzerland (2023)
9. hochschulkompass Stiftung zur Förderung der Hochschulrektorenkonferenz: Studium - fernstudium, <https://www.hochschulkompass.de/studium/rund-ums-studieren/studienformen/fernstudium.html>
10. Hoq, M., Brusilovsky, P., Akram, B.: Analysis of an explainable student performance prediction model in an introductory programming course. In: Feng, M., Käser, T., Talukdar, P. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Educational Data Mining*. pp. 79–90. International Educational Data Mining Society, Bengaluru, India (July 2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8115693>
11. Merceron, A., Dogaru, T., Waghela, R., Sauer, P.: Predicting dropout in an online degree across two institutions - a case study. In: *Proceedings of the Machine Learning and Principles and Practice of Knowledge Discovery in Databases - International Workshops of ECML PKDD 2024*. Springer Cham (2024), https://prof.bht-berlin.de/fileadmin/prof/merceron/Artikel/RKDE_2024_NewFormatCameraready.pdf

12. Moreno-Marcos, P.M., Alario-Hoyos, C., Muñoz-Merino, P.J., Kloos, C.D.: Prediction in moocs: A review and future research directions. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies* **12**, 384–401 (2019), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:69950054>
13. Rotelli, D., Monreale, A.: Time-on-task estimation by data-driven outlier detection based on learning activities. In: LAK22: 12th International Learning Analytics and Knowledge Conference. p. 336–346. LAK22, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3506860.3506913>
14. Rotelli, D., Monreale, A.: Processing and understanding moodle log data and their temporal dimension. *Journal of Learning Analytics* **10**, 126–141 (Aug 2023). <https://doi.org/10.18608/jla.2023.7867>
15. Tempelaar, D.T., Rienties, B., Giesbers, B.: In search for the most informative data for feedback generation: Learning analytics in a data-rich context. *Computers in Human Behavior* **47**, 157–167 (2015). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.05.038>
16. Wöhrle, J., Karolyi, H., Weidlich, J., Blanc, B., Woick, A.: Wechselwirkungen zwischen digitalisierter hochschulbildung und studienerefolg. In: Wissenschaftskonferenz: Studieneerfolg durch Digitalisierung? FernUniversität in Hagen (2024), <https://www.fernuni-hagen.de/forschung/schwerpunkte/catalpa/aktuelles-terme/aktuelles/wissenschaftskonferenz-lamass.shtml>
17. Švábenský, V., Verger, M., Rodrigo, M.M.T., Monterozo, C.J.G., Baker, R.S., Saavedra, M.Z.N.L., Lallé, S., Shimada, A.: Evaluating algorithmic bias in models for predicting academic performance of filipino students. In: Paassen, B., Epp, C.D. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Educational Data Mining*. pp. 744–751. International Educational Data Mining Society, Atlanta, Georgia, USA (July 2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12729936>